

D1.5 Dissemination, Communications and Exploitation – Interim Report

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Abstract**Key Words**

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The Dissemination, Communications and Exploitation Interim Report (D1.5) evaluates the project's dissemination, communication, and exploitation strategies from M1 to M15, aligning these efforts with the objectives and KPIs outlined in the Description of Action (DoA) and initial DCE plan (D1.2). The report details the establishment of communication channels such as the project website, social media, branding, publications, and events, and examines activities related to each Key Exploitable Result. It also looks ahead to the M15–30 period, outlining future activities and assessing potential challenges that could impact ongoing dissemination, communication, and exploitation efforts.

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Terminology / Acronyms	
Terminology / Acronym	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMB	Activity Management Board
CoP	Community of Practice
CM	Communications Manager
DB	Database
DCE	Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation
DoA	Description of Action
DocDB	EGI Document Database
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EAB	External Advisory Board
EM	Exploitation Manager
GA	General Assembly
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HEP	High Energy Physics
HTC	High-Throughput Computing
HPC	High Performance Computing
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MS	Milestone
PD	Project Director
PM	Project Manager
PMO	Project Management Office
PO	Project Objective
PY	Project Year
QRM	Quality and Risk Manager
RA	Radio Astronomy

RI	Research Infrastructure
SRIDA	Strategic Research, Innovation and Deployment Agenda
SSO	Single Sign On
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

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Executive summary

The Dissemination, Communications and Exploitation Interim Report (D1.5) evaluates the specific dissemination, communication and exploitation strategies and measures that have been conducted by the project among the project stakeholders in M1 – M15, and gives an overview of the concrete actions and activities executed by the project. It includes an updated overview of the objectives of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Tasks (1.3 and 2.3) in relation with the SPECTRUM main expected outcomes and KPIs as identified in the DoA and in the initial DCE plan (D1.2).

The document gives an overview of the communication channels and tools that have been established by the project, including the website and social media, branding, website, planned publications, and events.

It provides an overview of activities for each Key Exploitable Result (Stakeholders, Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication).

Finally, it looks forward to the activities projected in M15–30, as well as an assessment of the current challenges that could influence the dissemination, communication and exploitation activities related to the project.

1. Introduction

The Dissemination Communications, and Exploitation Interim Report (D1.5) offers a comprehensive evaluation of the dissemination, communication, and exploitation strategies implemented by the project during the period from M1 to M15. This report provides a detailed overview of the specific measures and activities undertaken to engage project stakeholders effectively. It aligns these efforts with the objectives of the Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Tasks (1.3 and 2.3), ensuring they support the main expected outcomes and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) outlined in the Description of Action (DoA) and the initial Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation (DCE) plan (D1.2).

The document highlights the establishment and utilization of various communication channels and tools, including the project website, social media platforms, branding initiatives, planned publications, and events. It also delves into the activities related to each Key Exploitable Result, focusing on stakeholders, exploitation, dissemination, and communication.

Looking ahead, the report outlines the planned activities for the M15–30 period and assesses the current challenges and issues that may impact future dissemination, communication, and exploitation efforts related to the project.

2. Dissemination, Communications and Exploitation Progress

2.1. Dissemination, Communications and Exploitation Channels Update

2.1.1. Communication Toolkit update

The core project branding, established in the second month of the project (M02), has not undergone any changes. The project has designed a moo card, roll-up, basic poster and flyer. In addition, a dedicated logo for SPECTRUMCoP has been developed to make the activity stand out.

The [Generic Slidedeck](#) has been updated with detailed slides for all work packages and includes now useful overview slides to be used for keynotes and shorter presentations. This allows all partners to present the project at events, adding their own slides if necessary.

2.1.2. Project website

The project website, established at the end of M01, has received 2 846 unique visitors at the end of M15, with 5,788 pageviews.

Figure 1: Website visits since the launch (February 6 2024)

Currently, the website mainly collects news items about events, SPECTRUMCoP – the Community of Practice (CoP) – and partner activities. Once the first results are published, more in-depth articles based on the deliverables will be published. Other information pages (such as the KER pages) will be updated as well. A first proposal to populate the KER pages with a new set of logos is being executed in March 2025 (see [Annex 3: KER Icons \(proposal\)](#)). A Zenodo integration will ensure that all publications (including deliverables) added to Zenodo are shown on the website as outputs.

2.1.3. Social Media

The primary social media channel for SPECTRUM is [LinkedIn](#). Engagement numbers on LinkedIn are according to expectations, with 208 followers and 7511 impressions at the end of M14, with an average monthly engagement rate of 8.6%.

The project stays behind its initial decision not to go forward with an account on X given the status of the network in general. The project is experimenting with a [BlueSky account](#), for now only with limited engagement. To facilitate sharing of video, the project has established [its own YouTube channel](#) (moving away from the initial plan of only having a guest channel on the EGI Foundation main YouTube account).

Figure 2: LinkedIn engagement rate M2-M12

Further metrics and an overview of the related KPIs are found in [Table 1: Dissemination and Communication Metrics and KPIs](#) (chapter 3.1).

2.1.4. Events

2.1.4.1. External events

All outreach activities need to be reported according to the following procedure: events are signalled during WP- and AMB-meetings, and further discussed during PMO meetings if needed. All partners are encouraged to share their planned events through a dedicated procedure on Confluence.

The first year of the project, 2024, allowed us to create a database of yearly returning events on Confluence. During AMB meetings, partners are requested to signal any additional events they will attend, including closed meetings and ad hoc events. The communication team will increase the effort to report back on these events via LinkedIn and the website, and to make sure that all presentations and other materials are captured on Zenodo.

During the first 12 months of the project, the SPECTRUM event strategy focused on building brand recognition: handing out flyers and being present at booths, raising awareness about the SPECTRUMCoP launch (M5) and present the work of SPECTRUMCoP (KER1), to announce future project outputs (KER2, KER3, KER4), and to lay the basis for dissemination of the final project outputs, the SRIDA and the Blueprint (KER5 and KER6).

In the second half of the project, event presence will focus on the presentation of the outputs released at M15 (KER2, KER3, KER4) and announcing the SRIDA and Technical Blueprint (KER5, KER6) with the objective to gather feedback for their final versions and gain traction to support their adoption. SPECTRUM will continue to be present at conference booths hosted by project coordinator EGI Foundation.

The project has organised and hosted the session [Roadmapping for high energy physics and radio astronomy](#) at EGI2024, with a presence of more than 40 participants.

Introductory presentations about SPECTRUM have been given at high-profile events such as the Einstein Telescope Computing Workshop, ATLAS Computing Week, [CHEP2024](#), [IBERGRID2024](#), the [Advanced Computing User Day 2024](#), and the EUROHPC Summit 2025. Furthermore, SPECTRUM partners have discussed SPECTRUM at high-profile meetings¹ and events such as the [EuroHPC Summit 2024](#), ESCAPE Open Collaboration EB Meeting, various HEP/HPC Strategy Meetings, ISC High Performance (ISC) 2024, 9th PUNCH4NFDI General Meeting, [EOSC Symposium 2024](#), and the [EuroHPC User Day 2024](#).

Further event presence included participation in (shared) event booths hosted by SPECTRUM Partners at [ISC 2024](#), [TERATEC Forum 2024](#), [TNC2024](#), [EGI2024](#), CHEP2024, Supercomputing 2024, [EUDAT2024](#) and [HiPEAC 2025](#).

2.1.4.2. Plans for M15–30

In the second half of the project, SPECTRUM will continue to be present at relevant events with talks, posters, and participation in exhibition booths. The expectation is that, with a range of concrete outputs now available, project partners will be able to target more specifically relevant Call for Proposals, resulting in more in-depth talks and sessions at key events, as well as more invitations to closed meetings. For example, SPECTRUM will be part of a keynote presentation given by CERN at the EuroHPC Summit 2025, and the project has a BoF session accepted at ISC 2025.

¹ some of these meetings were invitation-only and have no public agenda

The public project end meeting will take place in June 2026: this is intended to be a stand-alone and high profile event attracting the stakeholders who need to be aware of the outcomes of the project and are expected to implement them.

2.1.4.3. Internal project meetings

A first in-person project meeting was [the kick off, organised in Amsterdam](#) on January 30th 2024. A first virtual all-hands meeting took place on June 11, 2024. A [second in person all-hands meeting](#) took place during EGI2024 on September 30th, 2024, while [a third in-person AHM](#) was hosted by CERN in January 2025. During this AHM, a dedicated communication and dissemination workshop helped partners to conduct a network analysis and a preparation exercise for the dissemination of the SRIDA and Technical Blueprint at the end of the project. ([workspace for the workshop](#)).

2.1.5. Publications

The standard publication repository for SPECTRUM outputs (including deliverables, presentations, scientific publications, and posters) will be deposited in [the SPECTRUM Zenodo repository](#). The Zenodo analytics tools will also be used to assess views and downloads for all publications. The three public deliverables on Zenodo have been viewed 117 times and downloaded 102 times at the end of M13. During M14–15, a campaign targeting partners, as part of the event registration strategy, will push partners to upload their presentations to Zenodo as well. Until now, no scientific publications have resulted from the project.

2.2. Stakeholder Engagement

In D1.2, we have identified the main and secondary stakeholder groups for the SPECTRUM Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation activities.

During a workshop at the January 2025 AHM, we conducted a network analysis that consolidates our initial assessment (see [Annex 4: Network analysis \(January 2025 Brainstorm\)](#)).

- Target Group 1 (TG1): Scientific Communities and Research Infrastructures

In High Energy Physics, Radio Astronomy and adjacent domains (such as HPC). This group includes SPECTRUM project partners, their ecosystems. They need to be aware of the project, and are expected to take up and implement project outputs. Representatives actively engage with the project via membership of SPECTRUMCoP and its Working Groups

- Target Group 2 (TG2): Computing & Data Service Providers & e-Infrastructures

Existing Data, HPC, HTC, Cloud, Quantum and other Compute service providers, infrastructures and facilities at national and EU level. This group includes SPECTRUM project partners. They need to be aware of the project, and are expected to take up and implement project outputs. Representatives actively engage with the project via membership of SPECTRUMCoP and its Working Groups.

- Target Group 3 (TG3): Policy Makers and Funders

This group includes, but is not limited to, stakeholders such as the European Commission, EuroHPC, EOSC, National Authorities and ESFRIs. They need to be aware of the project, and are one of the target groups of the SPECTRUM SRIDA. They need to be closely engaged with the project to provide input and align policies, and to take up its outputs.

As there is no action expected from them at consultation level, the secondary target groups as identified in T1.2 will be reached by the project as a consequence of the activities targeting the main stakeholders (through events and social media).

- TG4: Researchers from the ‘long tail of science’
- TG5: Research Institutions/Universities/Industry/SMEs
- TG6: General Public

As shown in chapter 2.3, TG1 and TG2 have been targeted extensively during M1-15 through the KER1 and KER2 and 3 and 4 activities. Logically, TG3 will be a core target group for the DCE activities planned in M15-M30 for KER5 and KER6.

2.3. Exploitation

2.3.1. KER1: SPECTRUMCoP

2.3.1.1. Stakeholders

Target Groups: (TG1) Scientific Communities within RIs with data-intensive computing needs, with a focus on RA and HEP.

2.3.1.2. KER Components

- Knowledge Hub (Neovia - T3.1 Leader)
 - Content in the [SPECTRUM Community of Practice Home](#)²
 - [Document Repository](#)² Page
 - SPECTRUMCoP Google Drive
 - [Useful Material](#)² of the project
- Charter & Governance Structure rule (INFN - T3.2 Leader)
 - [SPECTRUMCoP Charter](#)² - Governance Structure
- Collaboration Platform (EGI - T1.1)
 - Confluence: [SPECTRUM Community of Practice Home](#)²
 - Mailing lists
- Marketing & Branding (EGI - T1.3)
 - <https://www.spectrumproject.eu/spectrumcop>
 - Logos, Presentations

2.3.1.3. Exploitation Plan Progress & Activities:

A Community charter has been established early in the project to establish and regulate the collaboration³ that includes the commitment to contribute and provide input to the SPECTRUM project.

JENA (Joint activity ECFA-NuPECC-APPEC) is an interest group that shares the same objectives as the SPECTRUM CoP in the HEP, Astrophysics and Nuclear Physics domains. They launched several Working Groups including JENA-HPC - in line with SPECTRUM CoP Working Groups. Key Experts from JENA have been invited to be part of SPECTRUM CoP and reports & information generated was shared across groups. They held a workshop last year: JENA Computing Workshop⁴ and are organizing a follow up event in 2025. As a result the work done linked to the SPECTRUM CoP survey has been incorporated into the JENA-HPC

² Restricted to the consortium members

³ <https://cdn.spectrumproject.eu/app/uploads/2024/03/SPECTRUMCoP-final.pdf>

⁴ <https://agenda.infn.it/event/34738/>

technical report that will be used as a content for the discussions held for the future JENA Computing Workshop.

On top of that, a digested summary of the work done under WP3 and the feedback collected from SPECTRUMCoP has been used as Contribution to the European Strategy for Particle Physics⁵ organized by CERN which happens every 6 years and the collection of input has started by the end of 2024.

2.3.2. Dissemination & Communication Update

Targeting members of Scientific Communities within RIs with data-intensive computing needs, with a focus on RA and HEP, SPECTRUMCoP has received a dedicated [webpage](#), with information about the Working Groups and the Charter, and a call to action to join. [A news item](#) has been published on the website. To increase awareness and to make the Community of Practice stand out, a dedicated branding for SPECTRUMCoP has been developed. Activating the partner network, posts on [LinkedIn](#) and mailing lists (such as the [April 2024 EGI newsletter](#)), as well as direct mails and personal contacts, served to recruit members for SPECTRUMCoP and responses for the [first survey](#) (in collaboration with JENA).

A Call To Action to join SPECTRUMCoP has also been added to the project flyers that have been distributed at various events (see [Annex 1: Events](#)), and key messages plus a call to action ('Join SPECTRUMCoP) have been added as a slide into the [general slide deck](#) (p 30). The SPECTRUMCoP has therefore received attention at all events attended by SPECTRUM partners (see annex for full list).

A knowledge base for SPECTRUMCoP members has been added to [Confluence](#)⁶.

2.3.3. Plans for M15–30

During the next period SPECTRUMCoP will continue under WP4. Dissemination-wise continuous attention via news items to SPECTRUMCoP activities. Dissemination and Communication: SPECTRUMCoP will be followed up continuously by posting blog and LinkedIn posts related to the work done. Towards the end of the project, a dedicated communication package will be prepared for them, allowing them to disseminate the final project results into their own network. This will not only be distributed online, but will be complemented at the final event with a 'paper' version of the SRIDA). SPECTRUMCoP experts will be key stakeholders for the SPECTRUM final event

Exploitation-wise, it is expected to increase the involvement of SPECTRUMCoP, not only to increase the expert contributions to the project but also to increase the usefulness of the community itself for the members. Working groups will be re-defined if necessary (Milestone 6). It is expected that their contribution will be integrated towards final deliverables (Technical Blueprint, and SPECTRUM SRIDA) and to keep helping to define the strategy within HEP and increase the contribution towards RA communities.

⁵ <https://europeanstrategy.cern/>

⁶ Restricted to the consortium members

2.4. KER2, KER3 and KER4 (WP5 Related)

2.4.1. Stakeholders:

(TG1) Scientific Communities within RIs with data-intensive computing needs, with a focus on RA and HEP;
(TG2) Computing & Data Service Providers & e-Infrastructures.

2.4.2. Components

- KER 2. Compendium of Use Cases [All use cases descriptions](#)
 - HEP Use Cases: The CMS LHC experiment (click [here](#)), ATLAS, LHCb, ALICE, AI-based particle flow reconstruction (MLPF), LLMs for CERN accelerator complex, Lattice Quantum Chromodynamics,
 - RA Use Cases: The Power Spectrum of 21 cm HI Fluctuations (SKAO), The Star Formation History of the Universe (SKAO), Extragalactic Surveys (LOFAR), Fast Radio Bursts and Transients,
 - Other Use Cases: MISTRAL (Meteo Italian Supercomputing Portal), LIGATE Molecular Dynamics, eBRAINS
- KER3. List of all European Compute & Data e-Infrastructures for Research, including the analysis of the technical capabilities, best practices, a description of software and hardware components especially suited to address the problems of the communities (formulated in KER2), and policies for federated compute and data continuum.
- KER4. A list of related Access Policies of European Compute & Data e-Infrastructures for Research including interoperability aspects and the analysis on how they can be used by project related scientific communities.
- Contact Database including related member organizations and their key roles.

2.4.3. Exploitation Plan Progress & Activities

Main exploitation of WP5-related KERs are linked to the use, adoption and uptake within the project:

- Contribution to KER1: All generated use cases become part of the Knowledge Hub to be shared with SPECTRUM CoP ready to be used and re-used by their members.
- Contribution to KER 5 (Blueprint Architecture) and KER 6 (SRIDA): Digested analysis, recommendations and gaps will become part of the key documents of SPECTRUM

The compendium of use cases, landscape and access policies analysis will also be interesting for project external stakeholders:

- KER2 is also contributing to the knowledge transfer to JENA initiative, to The European Strategy for Particle Physics (CERN) and to any equivalent initiatives happening within Radio Astronomy, such as PUNCH4NFDI, RadioNet, etc.
- Also on the infrastructure side it can become part of the EuroHPC consultations – as part of the EuroHPC user forum represented by SPECTRUM Partners, as well as other key communities and advocacy groups in the HPC and Advanced Computing Continuum – such as ETP4HPC, HiPEAC

Relevant contacts from the different e-Infrastructures will be invited to become part of the SPECTRUMCoP (KER1) so they can also leverage the rest of the project outputs.

2.4.4. Dissemination & Communication Update

Key messages (including a description of the intended result and a timeline) have been added to the [general slide deck](#). The network and structures to promote consultations and surveys are in place and ready to go into production (web pages, mailing list, social media). Preparatory work has been made to propose a publication-ready version of the use cases, but it needs to be investigated if all information can be made public.

2.4.5. Plans for M15–30

Dissemination and Communication: D5.1 (Representative use cases: analysis and alignment) will be published on March 31, 2025, and will receive dedicated attention via the website and SPECTRUM LinkedIn, with a visual, a summarising blogpost and a blurb. All partners will receive a communication package related to the M15 deliverables, including suggested social media posts, talking points, and a visual, with the request to distribute it as widely as possible in their own networks. A summarising webinar presenting the work done in the first half of the project will be scheduled in Q2 of 2025.

Exploitation-wise will continue the activities towards engaging the different relevant stakeholders internal and external to the project. Successful exploitation will grant recommendations and information is duly reflected in the Technical Blueprint and SRIDA – and available towards the SpectrumCoP and rest of interested external stakeholders.

2.5. KER5: Technical Blueprint

2.5.1. Stakeholders

(TG1) Scientific Communities within RIs with data-intensive computing needs, with a focus on RA and HEP;
(TG2) Computing & Data Service Providers & e-Infrastructures.

2.5.2. Exploitation Plan Progress & Activities

While this result is functional to develop the SRIDA (KER6), it will be of great interest for other research communities and computing providers, to be able to plan their roadmap for development of new technologies and services to cover the future needs of the scientific communities. At the time of writing this deliverable all the exploitation related activities were linked to those activities and KERs that will be used during the second half of the project to generate Technical Blueprint Document.

2.5.3. Dissemination & Communication Update

In line with the project timing, there have not been targeted Dissemination & Communication activities yet related to the Technical Blueprint. However, the Blueprint has been presented as one of the intended project outcomes at the various presentations given throughout the course of M1–15. A network analysis intended to identify target audiences for the dissemination of this result, as well as a knowledge base of best practices of how to engage these audiences with the result, has been the subject of a dedicated exercise conducted with project partners during the January 2025 AHM (see [Annex 1: Events](#)).

2.5.4. Plans for M15–30

Dissemination and communication: Towards the end of the project, a dedicated communication package will be prepared for project partners and SPECTRUMCoP members, allowing them to disseminate the final project results into their own network. At the final event, date and location tbd, SPECTRUMCoP, partners and invited stakeholders, will receive a physical ‘package’ with printables, including the Blueprint report and SRIDA.

Exploitation-wise – it is going to be crucial to get the commitment of both scientific communities and e-Infrastructures to adopt the technical requirements that will emerge from the Technical Blueprint.

2.6. KER6 – SRIDA

2.6.1. Stakeholders:

(TG1) Scientific Communities and RIs with data-intensive computing needs, with a focus on RA and HEP;
(TG2) Computing and Data Service Providers and e-Infrastructures; (TG3) Policy Makers / Funding Bodies.

2.6.2. Exploitation Plan Progress & Activities

By the comprehensive analysis of all previously described KERs are feeding the SRIDA. Hence it is the most relevant result. It will need to be properly disseminated across all relevant stakeholders as described in the previous section, especially to the policy makers and funding bodies so that they can be duly addressed in the next work programmes. All partners from the consortium are fully committed to endorse the future take up of the technologies and services described in the roadmap and bring into their own implementation plans and access and use them for their future scientific needs. This will lead to the future integration of enhanced services to EOSC available for RIs. At the time of writing this deliverable all the exploitation related activities were linked to those activities and KERs that will be used during the second half of the project to generate.

2.6.3. Dissemination & Communication Update

In line with the project timing, there have not been targeted Dissemination & Communication activities yet related to the SRIDA. However, the Blueprint has been presented as one of the intended project outcomes at the various presentations given throughout the course of M1–15. A network analysis intended to identify target audiences for the dissemination of this result, as well as a knowledge base of best practices of how to engage these audiences with the result, has been the subject of a dedicated exercise conducted with project partners during the January 2025 AHM (see [annex 2](#) and the [mural](#)).

2.6.4. Plans for M15–30

Dissemination and communication: Towards the end of the project, a dedicated communication package will be prepared for project partners and SPECTRUMCoP members, allowing them to disseminate the final project results into their own network. At the final event, date and location tbd, SPECTRUMCoP, partners and invited stakeholders, will receive a physical ‘package’ with printables, including the Blueprint report and SRIDA.

Exploitation-wise – a successful adoption of the SRIDA will need the engagement of policy makers and funding bodies to adopt the recommendations highlighted at the SRIDA to ensure the necessary technologies and infrastructure is ready and available in a timely manner.

3. Impact

3.1. Dissemination and Communications Metrics

Table 1 shows an overview of the key communication and dissemination channels and their current (M14) reach and impact, mapped against the KPI values set in D1.2.

Table 1: Dissemination and Communication Metrics and KPIs

Channel	Metric	M30 target value	M6 value	M15 value
Website	Pageviews	500 per month	337	413
LinkedIn	Followers	300 at the end of the project	95	214
LinkedIn	Engagement per post	8% ⁷	8%	8.6%
Newsletter	Subscriptions	120	28	29
Events	Number of international events with project presence	30	8	24
Workshops and Webinars	Number (online and in person)	6	n.a.	1
Workshops and Webinars	Satisfaction score	4.5/5	n.a.	8.1/10 (EG12024 overall satisfaction score)
Publications	Downloads and views of project publications (Scientific publications, presentations, public deliverables)	50 views 15 downloads	n.a.	117 views 102 downloads

⁷ Note that engagement % typically decreases when follower count increases

3.2. Exploitation Achievement Indicators

Table 2 shows an overview of the current (M15) achievement indicators for every KER, mapped against the target value set in the DoA and expanded on in D1.2.

Table 2: Exploitation Achievement Indicators and KPIs

Key Exploitable Result	Achievements Indicators	Means of Verification	Target Value (DoA)	M15 Value
KER1	Number of established Working Groups	Published on the project website under SPECTRUM CoP section: https://www.spectrumproject.eu/spectrumcop/	5	6
KER1	Number of participants in the Community of Practice	Published on the project website under SPECTRUM CoP section: https://www.spectrumproject.eu/spectrumcop/	30 stretched to 50	65 unique participants, 119 in total
KER1	Number of entities that contributed inputs to the Technical Blueprint and SRIDA	The consolidated reports for each consultation cite the number of inputs received, qualified by type of contribution	No value provided in DoA. We can take 50 as baseline target	0 (SRIDA expected at M30)
KER1	Number of institutions that signed the community charter	Community charter published in the project website: https://cdn.spectrumproject.eu/app/uploads/2024/03/SPECTRUMCoP-final.pdf community charter is accepted by the participants (hence not signed, but participants and their affiliations are shortlisted in the web https://www.spectrumproject.eu/spectrumcop	No value provided in DoA. We can take 30 as baseline target	24
KER2	Number of data-intensive science use cases agreed and analysed	Described in project deliverable D5.1 Representative use cases: analysis and alignment (T5.1, KER2)	10	17

KER2	Technology time horizon considered (years)	Time horizon of forecast for technology evolution considered in the report D5.1 Representative use cases: analysis and alignment (T5.1, KER2)	Section in the report	Short and long-term being considered (2–3 and 5–10 years)
KER3	Number of analysed large-scale European providers (HPC, Cloud, HTC, data) for the landscape analysis	Described in project deliverable D5.3 Landscape of RIs: technologies, services, gaps (T5.3, KER3)	15	15 According to plan (updated upon submission of WP5 deliverables)
KER3	Number of gaps identified	Described in project deliverable 5.3 Landscape of RIs: technologies, services, gaps (T5.3, KER3)	15	Will be provided upon submission of WP5 deliverables
KER4	Number and extent of RIs and scientific communities taken into account	Document covering existing access policies and gaps. Described in project deliverable. D5.2 Interoperable access policies: analysis and recommendations. (T5.2, KER4) (Expected – M15)	No value provided in DoA. We can take 2 scientific communities as baseline target (RA and HEP), and 5 RIs	5 (RE, HEP) and the ones represented by EBRAINS, LIGATE and MISTRAL
KER4	Number and coverage of European providers/centres for HPC, Cloud, HTC, Quantum, or data	Availability of the recommendation document to the public. Described in project deliverable. D5.2 Interoperable access policies: analysis and recommendations. (T5.2, KER4) (Expected – M15) Deliverable to be publicly accessible from Zenodo (Expected – M15)	15	15 According to plan (updated upon submission of WP5 deliverables)
KER5	Number of entities that contributed inputs to the Technical Blueprint (from the CoP or other channels)	Result from the consultation process for inputs and public draft D6.1 Technical Blueprint for Compute and Data Continuum (T6.2, KER5) (Expected – M30)	50	0 (Blueprint expected M30)

KER5	Number of capabilities aligned across communities	Described in project deliverable D6.1 Technical Blueprint for Compute and Data Continuum (T6.2, KER5) (Expected - M30)	10	0 (Blueprint expected M30)
KER5	Identification of cross-cutting research practices, technical and capital resource requirements for accelerating new insights and scientific discovery.	Described in project deliverable D6.1 Technical Blueprint for Compute and Data Continuum (T6.2, KER5) (Expected - M30)	10	0 (Blueprint expected M30)
KER6	The SRIDA is agreed and supported by the CoP	Result from the consultation process for inputs and public draft D7.1 SPECTRUM Strategy Research Innovation and Deployment Agenda (T7.2, KER6) (Expected - M30)	No value provided in DoA. SRIDA endorsed by SPECTRUMCoP	0 (SRIDA expected M30)
KER6	Number of entities that contributed inputs to the SRIDA (from the CoP or other channels)	Result from the consultation process for inputs and public draft. D7.1 SPECTRUM Strategy Research Innovation and Deployment Agenda (T7.2, KER6) Expected - M30)	50	0 (SRIDA expected M30)

4. Next Steps. Plans M15–M30

4.1. Dissemination and Communication

With the branding and communication toolkit in place, the main focus for RP2 will be on the updating of the website and the promotion of the interim deliverables and of KER5 and KER6 on the website, social media and other online channels. As we have been collecting mail addresses, we will also start creating a semi-regular newsletter update about the published deliverables.

In addition, 'new' formats such as webinar and a video clip will in all probability be added to the range of dissemination measures, as well as a published version of the final deliverables (format tbd).

4.1.1. Communication Toolkit

The branding and tools in the communication toolkit will remain in place. Further elements will be added, such as the design of specific icons for the KERs (see [Annex 3](#)) and designs for posters, flyers and roll-ups to update our events presence with a representation of actual project outputs (rather than generic project information).

4.1.2. Project Website

On the project website, the results pages will be expanded (KERs pages) and added to (detailed deliverable descriptions). The website back-end will continue to receive adaptations according to the project needs.

4.1.3. Social Media

LinkedIn will remain our main channel. We will continue to explore the BlueSky options, and experiment with ways to generate more traction. The YouTube channel will receive more attention once we will organise our own webinars. We will also create a final video clip to promote the Blueprint and SRIDA.

4.1.4. Events

T2.3 will continue to analyse the project landscape for suitable opportunities for events to present the project interim and final deliverables. In the second half of the project, event presence will focus on the presentation of the outputs released at M15 (KER2, KER3, KER4) and announcing the SRIDA and Technical Blueprint (KER5, KER6) with the objective to gather feedback for their final versions and gain traction to support their adoption. SPECTRUM will continue to be present at conference booths hosted by project coordinator EGI Foundation.

Current opportunities that are already identified are ISC2025, where we will host a so-called 'BoF session' and a booth presence at EGI2025. Participation in CHEP2026, SKAO Science Meeting and the EuroHPC User Days (tbd) are also considered. As the list with planned events is growing, we expect to be able to present our outcomes and deliverables at least at 20 more events, exceeding our target KPI of 30 events. Currently, T2.5 is scouting for a location and potential co-location for a high-profile closing event, targeting all stakeholders (M30).

The focus on event presence is in line with what is reported during the Communications Brainstorm organised in January 2025 during the AHM (see [mural](#)): a large part of our audience consume information such as we intend to distribute (SRIDA, Blueprint) via one-on-one contacts at events, as well as through event presentations.

The project will organise a series of webinars presenting the main project outcomes, starting with the first series of deliverables. These webinars will be timed to ensure more traction for the final event outputs (so with a clear CTA associated with them).

4.1.5. Publications

Any scientific publications will be monitored and provided as open access through our Zenodo project community.

4.2. Challenges

Based on the SPECTRUM project's progress and emerging results, funding bodies such as the European Commission, EuroHPC, and national organizations can leverage the project's findings in two key ways:

- Utilize the comprehensive analysis conducted by SPECTRUM, which is grounded in the experiences of two major scientific communities and encompasses various other domains. This analysis includes community needs, use cases, landscape, and access analysis, which are available in the project deliverables at the 15-month mark.
- Incorporate the forward-looking vision and recommendations that will be provided through the Technical Blueprint and the Strategic Research, Innovation, and Deployment Agenda (SRIDA). These documents will outline future opportunities and needs in data-intensive scientific collaborations across Europe.

To maximize the impact of these insights, funding bodies should:

- Actively engage with ongoing SPECTRUM project activities to ensure that necessary programs are established in a timely manner.
- Consider the project's goal of creating an Exabyte-scale research data federation and compute continuum when developing funding strategies.
- Align future funding initiatives with the SPECTRUM project's focus on elevating data-intensive science in Europe, particularly in fields such as High Energy Physics and Radio Astronomy.
- Use the project's findings to inform the development of funding programs that support the uptake of FAIR data analysis and open science practices.

By leveraging the SPECTRUM project's outcomes, funding bodies will be in the position to support Research Infrastructures to better address the unprecedented data processing, simulation, and analysis needs anticipated in frontier research over the coming decade.

5. Annexes

Annex 1: Events

Table 3: Events list (M1-M15)

Event Name	Start Date	KERs	Aim
<u>ETP4HPC Conference - Sassenheim (near amsterdam)</u>	13/02/2024	Mainly: KER1, Also KER3, KER5, KER6	Access to HPC community
<u>EuroHPC Summit 2024</u>	18/03/2024	Mainly: KER1, Also KER3, KER5, KER6	Access to HPC community Promotion SPECTRUMCoP
<u>ISC 2024 - Hamburg</u>	12/05/2024	Mainly: KER1, Also KER3, KER5, KER6	Major HPC event in Europe Promotion SPECTRUMCoP
<u>Teratec Conference</u>	29/05/2024	Mainly: KER1, Also: KER3, KER5,	Access to Advanced Computing Community in France Industry contacts Promotion SPECTRUMCoP
<u>EUBelgium24 RI Event</u>	04/06/2024	Mainly: KER1. Also: KER2, KER3, KER4	Increase visibility of project among RIs Networking Learn about upcoming RI policies and priorities
<u>TNC2024</u>	10/06/2024	Mainly: KER1, Also KER3, KER6	National and regional research and education networks, schools and universities, technology providers, and scientific projects Shared booth
<u>punch4-NFDI GA</u>	20/06/2024	Mainly: KER1. Also: KER2, KER3, KER4	Access to German Radio-Astronomy Community Promotion SPECTRUMCoP
<u>InPEX2024 Workshop</u>	17/06/2024	KER5, KER6	Policymakers - HPC community
<u>Einstein Telescope Computing Workshop</u> (internal)	8/07/2024	KER1	Promote the Survey Access to RA communities
<u>HEP/HPC Strategy Meeting - Europe</u> (internal)	06/09/2024	KER1, KER4, KER5, KER6	WP3, WP5
<u>EGI2024</u>	30/09/2024	All KERs	Access to EGI Community Curating session, Booth
ATLAS Computing Week (internal)	07/10/2024	KER1, KER2	Access to HEP Community
<u>IBERGRID 2024</u>	25/10/2024	KER5	Access to Advanced Computing in Spain and Portugal
<u>CHEP2024</u>	19/10/2024	Mainly: KER1, also	Major HEP event in Europe: booth,

		KER2	talks
<u>EOSC Symposium 2024</u>	21/10/2024	KER1, KER2, KER3, KER4	Access to policy makers (EOSC) in HEP and RA
<u>EuroHPC User Day 2024</u>	22/10/2024	KER1, KER2, KER3, KER4	Access to HPC community
<u>Supercomputing 2024</u>	12/11/2024	KER3, KER4	Access to Research infrastructures, e-infrastructures, Scientific Collaborations
ESCAPE Open Collaboration EB Meeting (internal)	28/11/2024	KER1, KER2	
<u>EUDAT 2024</u>	03/12/2024	KER1, KER2, KER3	Access to actors in the EOSC community, ESFRI, science clusters, and research infrastructures to get the latest on the state of the art and use cases of some of the core services for supporting European research
<u>Advanced Computing User Day</u>	12/12/2025	KER1, KER2, KER3, KER4	Access to Researchers who use advanced computing for their research Industry professionals, entrepreneurs, start-ups or SME's who use advanced computing Professionals at public administration
<u>HIPEAC 2025</u>	15/01/2025	KER2, KER3, KER4	Access to Advanced Computing Community in Spain Industry contacts Booth, Talk
<u>HEP/HPC Strategy Meeting - All Regions</u> (internal)	30/01/2025	KER1, KER5, KER6	WP3, WP5
<u>EuroHPC Summit 2025</u>	18/03/2025	KER3, KER4, KER5, KER6	Access to HPC community

Annex 2: Brainstorm (living document, captured from Confluence on 14/2)

(living document, captured from Confluence on 14/2):

<https://confluence.egi.eu/pages/viewpage.action?pageId=291342111>

Start confluence page

Mural link:

<https://app.mural.co/t/egi3550/m/egi3550/1736341273930/a1b5d58df403344c64ec3866a2a93a13ba81f03b>

Project Outputs Dissemination/Communication/Exploitation Brainstorm

This page is to collect ideas for and outputs of all dissemination/communication brainstorm

Objectives

- Complete our network analysis
- Identify potential gaps or updates for the CDE plan
- Provide an initiation to tech/science team

Results

Forward looking (Tech blueprint / SRIDA)

In a nutshell

3 main ways emerge from the partners experience and wishes to disseminate the BluePrint and SRIDA: onsite events, short web content and informal discussion. Video could be a path but shall be considered after a resource/benefit analysis.

On onsite event, quality of the speaker and interactive session maximises the dissemination, while on web content, a divide and conquer strategy shall be considered aiming to produce short formats as an entry point to the full documents, published in Open Access. There is a not-easy point on being well-referenced on generic platform (LinkedIn, Google) or trusted/well-known channels (newsletters, blogs...).

Finally informal discussion is an important channel that shall be investigated with a question for the DCE team on which material we can propose to enhance/leverage this channel.

Experience from the SPECTRUM partners

Part 1: internal survey on the most usual way to access to technical reports and contents

- On the question "What is your main source of information" (only one answer allowed), the partners answered:
 - Groups I am involved in – 6 answers
 - Self web search – 6 answers
 - My colleagues and institutions – 5 answers
 - No answer for "Other scientific groups" and "General information news and channels"
- On the question "What is your main format to access technical/scientific content?", the partners answered:
 - Conferences/workshops (onsite presentation) – 8 answers
 - Abstract – 7 answers
 - Coffee machine/afterwork (informal discussion) – 5 answers (from the room: we may have a favor from the Italian side on this one)
 - Reading the entire report (could be with AI) – 4 answers
 - Articles – 4 answers
 - Videos – 3 answers
 - Webinars or online presentations – 2 answers
 - Podcast – 0 answer

Part 2: "write your own story" – experiences of the partners on their most usual ways and best experience

Disclaimer for Mural: some inputs on "best experience" should probably be taken into consideration in the "most usual way" category

- On the most usual way: by far internet search wins the game. Informal discussion with colleagues is the second one. There are several ways in which the internet search is conducted, from "general" channels (LinkedIn or Google) to more specialised (ArXiv, NASA ADS) or own curated sources
- On best experience: in-presence events are taking the lion share here, with a taste for high-level (in terms of science but also communication skills) or interactive format. The second best is video (short format) with a podcast mention. Finally, open-access has also been mentioned as important

Intermediate conclusion from the partners experience

4 main actions seem to adequately disseminate the BluePrint and SRIDA dissemination:

- Presentation at onsite meetings
- Publication on the web
- Material to support informal dissemination
- Production of short video

4 paths seem to maximise/make it memorable

- For onsite meetings: either identify a very good speaker (technically and communicationally) or create an interactive session. If we have the resource to do so, we may also propose partners a short training on presentation/dedicate time to rehearsals to also enhance our own capacity
- For the web: focus on having an appealing abstract and (more difficult) to be well referenced in Google (should you cheat with Ads?) but also to find relays on well-known newsletters (EuroHPC...) – of course in Open Access . It has also been suggested in part 3 to propose different documents

rather than a "all in one" report focus on specific communities needs (and if they are interested, they will dig in :wink:)

- How to favor informal dissemination? We may think of a simple series of actions here: posters/flyers that can be put at the office and start the discussion or to suggest partners to organise informal events at their institution level...
- Video is a bit of paradox since it does not seem to be favored in a day-to-day basis, yet can be an appealing product → would take probably a lot of resources to have a catchy and short one → worth to think if we should go this way

Part 3: Ideas

- Mainly "classical" ideas with a clear emphasis on disseminating the project results at various events
- For the web, short and appealing material are clearly favored that could link to the full report, but there is a clear trend to produce short content (white paper, video...) as an entry point to raise interest

SPECTRUM Network analysis (Valentin)

In a nutshell

Participants were a little lost regarding the categories of the organisations, the links between them, and the scope of the project but succeeded in creating a list of the main stakeholders to disseminate the final deliverables of SPECTRUM.

In detail

- Scope: Participants were a little confused regarding the scope of the exercise: What does "stakeholders" mean? For what purpose? What does "dissemination" entail?
- Categories: Although we try to focus on identifying missing organisations, participants spent a lot of time debating how to categorise organisations. There were numerous discussions about how to sort organisations (especially the distinction between "organisations" and "facilities," or informal entities like JENA).
- Connections: The first groups attempted to link the organisations using different types of arrows, but the global map became a mess. The types of arrows defined by the second group were as follows: *Influence*, *Collaborate*, *Leverage*. However, it was too complicated and time-consuming to decide which type of connection was relevant for each organisation. As a result, subsequent groups decided to remove these arrows and group organisations by type.
- Exhaustiveness: Participants questioned whether including national organisations like NFDI on the map was relevant.
- Policy makers: The first group identified several policymakers, but next groups raised questions about this choice of including them.
- Use of Mural: While some of the other moderators chose to use Mural only to gather information, I chose to use it collaboratively: everyone could modify the map directly. Some participants used Mural for the first time, but long explanations were unnecessary as the tool is quite intuitive, so it turned out to be a good idea.
- Participation: In each group, one or two participants led the discussions, particularly when seated near the moderator or other active participants. A round table might have been more relevant for this type of exercise.

- Next steps: I still need to refine the organisation of the map a little, but the list of organisations is fairly accurate. As Sergio Andreozzi suggested, we could integrate this map (via a simple screenshot) into the next exploitation plan (deadline: end of March 2025).

Version of the global map just after the World café (version to be finalised)

Activities

- (Corentin LEFEVRE Valentin JAY BLANCHARD Xavier Salazar can you also add anything you need (post-its, cards, pens, ...)

General presentation of the workshop

Format: "DCE World Café"

- Introduction to the workshop (5')
- World café format:
 - Small groups of 4/5 people
 - Each group participates to each activity
 - Activity starts with 5' intro and instructions
 - Then there is a 15' work
 - Moderators: (Gwen, Xavier, Valentin, Corentin, Mariana)
 - Themes are:
 - Exploitation and innovation (Xavier)
 - "Transform the KERs into real impact"
 - "Do you master the Horizon Europe terms ? #JargonMaster)
 - Forward looking (Tech blueprint / SRIDA)
 - What shape will this take?
 - Deliverable group (KER2,3,4) (Gwen, Mariana Velho)
 - SPECTRUM Network analysis (Valentin)
 - Individual exercise to "map your network"
 - Also: when defining your activity, think we want to highlight it in our deliverable/report
:wink:
- Conclusion (5')
 - Brief summary by the activities moderators

Joint

Mural:

<https://app.mural.co/t/egi3550/m/egi3550/1736341273930/a1b5d58df403344c64ec3866a2a93a13ba81f03b>

Group composition

registrations (3).xlsx

Groups are preattributed to mix people between WPs, deliverables, communities

Exploitation and innovation – Transform the KERs into real impact for you

Objective: Refresh on the needed definitions for Exploitation according to the Grant Agreement and Assess Partners Expectations on how the project is useful for them. We don't want to be yet another presentation for partners to "disconnect" – but to maximize the usefulness of the project to the partners

- reminder about definitions exploitation/innovation
- high level discussion on what it would mean to them
- aim: if they know why, they have an incentive to tell us

Output: Per partner exploitation objectives

Materials: Short presentation on the computer + Dedicated confluence or Mural with the definitions, concepts, KERs and questions + Post-its & posters.

Activity (20')

Introduction – Reminder of usual HE terms & Jargon – definitions (5')

- Exploitation
- Result
- Outcome
- Impact

Discussion – What do they mean to you – how can they be useful to you? . What would be the questions that would be meaningful to you? How can we make it concrete & effective in your daily life? How can it be used effectively in the end (15')

- Why is the project useful to you & your organization ? (5')
- How do you and your organisation expect to use the results ? (5')
- What would you consider a successful outcome of the project ? (5')

Preparation of activity: forward looking (Tech Blueprint and SRIDA)

- Objective: gather current (best) practices on how our partners select, read and use information to build (best) dissemination scenarios for TechBlueprint and SRIDA
- Output: "Knowledge base" of the partners current (best) practices from themselves and their close environment and scenarios for DCE activities focused on TechBlueprint and SRIDA
- Materials: Presenting computer or video projector / Dedicated Confluence under the Dissemination root page (or another more convenient parent page) to gather the inputs → requires participants with connected computers [possible paper alternative] / Dedicated online questionnaire able to display live results / Mural

§ Improvements from the check-in meeting:

- Switch to the workshop Mural for the overall activity
- On Activity – part 1: simplify the questionnaire part + check with the timing to complete it – Simplification may come by lowering the number of options of the questionnaire (ex: when)

and/or by removing the questionnaire and focus on the story they would tell us on their classical and best experiences

- Activity (20'):
 - *Introduction (5')*
 - Explain the objective and rules of the session (3')
 - Share the appropriate Confluence page link and ensure partners are connected (2')
 - *Activity - Part 1 - Getting to know your (best) practices (around 4-5')*
 - Sub-objective: collect on the ground information on how partners get information and what they like best/they find attractive
 - What and how
 - Start with a short online questionnaire (3')
 - How do you access professional reports content?
 - From whom? (on a scale)
 - Groups you are involved/you work with (ex: SPECTRUM :wink:)
 - Your colleagues and institutions (ex: CERN)
 - External scientific groups (ex: IPCC)
 - General science information news and channels
 - When? (for each of the item - on a scale)
 - Hour of the day (before starting / morning / at lunch time / afternoon / after working hours / equally at any time)
 - Week of the day (monday / tuesday / wednesday / thursday / friday / week-end / equally at any day)
 - Week of the month (beginning / middle / end / equally at any time of the month) ****may be deleted****
 - Month of the year (january / february / march / april / may / june / july / august / september / october / november / december / on holidays / equally at any month) ****could be simplified per quarter****
 - Which format?
 - Abstract
 - All report reading
 - Articles
 - Webinars (online presentation)
 - Conferences and workshops (onsite presentation)
 - Coffee machine and Afterwork (informal discussion)
 - Videos
 - Podcasts
 - Any other support
 - Generally speaking, give us a description of you accessing pro report content (Ex: "in the morning train, reading on my mobile phone abstracts/articles I have pre-selected during my day at work" or "every Friday at lunch time on my computer at the office" or "attending

the same conference every year as the main moment during which I both assist to presentations and informally exchange with peers"...)

- How do your colleagues speak and share their works and results? (open question) ** to be refined and/or deleted? **
- End with two open questions (2')
 - In the last year, what has been your best report content experience? why (exceptional content, fun facts, attractive format, you were in a good mood...)?
 - In your entire career what was THE most memorable experience you had for a report content? why (personal strong links (publication of an important work), game-changer content, exceptionally dynamic event, very talented speaker...)?
- *Activity - Part 2 - Transferring your (best) practices in SPECTRUM (potential) DCE ideas and activities (around 5-6')*
 - Sub-objective: define DCE scenarios and ideas to give a fresh perspective and what we can do
 - Disclaimer: this is brainstorming material that will be used by DCE team, not promising we'll do them all :wink:
 - What and how
 - On the dedicated Confluence page: each participant fills in or modify DCE scenarios based on a table template indicating
 - Format
 - Channel
 - Best timing (if relevant)
 - Any Other
- *Conclusion (or not) (2')*
 - Depending on the group dynamics: take a short moment to wrap-up the ideas proposed
 - May be cancelled depending if the group is still working on

Activity: SPECTRUM Network analysis (Valentin)

Input (materials):

- Mural link provided in advance to participants via Slack, Indico and/or Confluence
- Pens and papers in case participants would like to take notes; video projector/computer screen to display the Mural (very optional).

1) Introduction and instructions (5')

- Objective: Get a global map of SPECTRUM stakeholders
- Definitions: network analysis, stakeholders
- Summary of previous sessions: Presentation of the Miro/Mural
- Opening questions:
 - How to represent and classify the network? By organisation category? By country? By involvement? By project?

- How to complete this network? How can we avoid gaps in this network? Are there any missing connections?
- Are there partners with whom we could collaborate further? How can we do this?

2) Network map (15')

- We complete the projected Mural map
- Dedicated space in the Mural to answer the following questions: How can this work be reused? How can it be communicated? Be integrated into deliverables?
- In case of difficulties: Tell participants to read the following Confluence page – <https://confluence.egi.eu/display/SPECTRUM/Stakeholder+analysis>

Output: Completed Mural

Results group (Gwen, Mariana Velho)

Input (materials): recording equipment; Mural , pens + post-its

Introduction and instructions: you are working on parts of the project. In this exercise, we want you to think about what parts of your work could be transformed into a communication, and in what form

Activity

- What can be taken out of the deliverables/result/milestone you are working on and onto the website/social media and how?
 - explain in one paragraph what the deliverable/result/milestone is about (recorded)
 - identify a topic for a news item
 - identify an angle for your institution that shows why you are partnering in SPECTRUM
 - think about a visualisation

Outputs:

- draft video's of people presenting their work
- topics for news items
- visualisation/output ideas

Brainstorm

List of ideas/activities/questions as they go without order or priority

- First things first: what are the outcomes expected by WP Com at the end of the workshop?
 - Messages from the project team on their results
 - Provide an initiation to the tech/science team on communication methods or jargons
 - Other (draft ?) communication materials ?

- How the partners think what they are doing should be communicated/promoted/told
- Complete our network analysis
- Shall we focus (only ?) on the project KERs approach?
- Do we have a list of well-identified outputs/results already available or to be available in the coming months
- Do we want to focus on storytelling? (ex: activity could be: prepare messages in advance corresponding to the results SPECTRUM wishes to disseminate – part of the workshop could be to ask to write a story about it)
- (too classical ?): potential activity – individually or by group: work on a result to write the key messages divided by main audience + pitch/oral session to sell them
- Could be a good idea to open the Horizon Europe dictionary and remind some jargons :wink:

What:

- Introduction/Sensitisation
- Individual exercise
 - Envision how the SRIDA could be shared to the world ?
 - Also be sure the techies have that part in their mind while working on the SRIDA :wink:
 - Ex: which format(s): flyer, 2 pagers, beautiful but long report...
 - +: what other strategies must/shall be impacted by the SRIDA ?
 - Do we only focus on SRIDA or do we open with other (if not all) KERs?
 - List of KERs we want to work on – or focus on M15 deliverables:
 - SRIDA (could be worked later on ?)
 - Tech blueprint (could be worked later on ?)
 - Compendium of UCs (Gwen: maybe group KER2,3,4?) → good idea :slight_smile:
 - Access policies ?
 - Compendium of existing approaches, services, solutions and policies
 - Another way to have it
 - Exploitation and innovation
 - "Transform the KERs into real impact"
 - "Do you master the Horizon Europe terms ? #JargonMaster)
 - Forward looking (Tech blueprint / SRIDA)
 - What shape will this take?
 - Compendia group (KER2,3,4)
 - What can be taken out of the deliverable and onto the website/social media and how?
 - SPECTRUM Network analysis (Stakeholders)
 - Individual exercise to "map your network"
 - Engage SPECTRUMCoP in dissemination?
 - Opinion: maybe not for this session
 - But: to be in the conversation while shifting from WP3 to WP4
 - And: this workshop could be duplicated in an online session with CoP(s)
- In small groups + world café format : Map the inputs of individual exercise to our plan (are there any gaps ?)
 - Use post-its to position the inputs of a predefined matrix (e.g communication plan)
 - Channel
 - Target audience

- Networks
- Message
- Format
- KPI
- + prepare in advance what is already on the communication plan (as a basis or as a reward)
- Could be part of the progress report (as update for the 2d half of the project)
- Groups:
 - 20-isch people on site
 - e.g 4*5 or 5*4
 - We have 5 potential moderators (Gwen, Xavier, Mariana, Valentin, Corentin)
 - Or random 2

+ exploitation – uptake / adoption

end of confluence page

Annex 3: KER Icons (proposal)

Community of Practice

SPECTRUMCoP, a Community of Practice of research infrastructures in physics, radio-astronomy and other scientific domains and related collaboration agreement

Compendium of Use Cases

Compendium of use cases, related challenges, gaps and requirements covering technical and policy aspects

Compendium of Existing Approaches, Services, Solutions and Policies

Compendium of existing approaches, existing services, technical solutions and policies for the federation of data and compute infrastructures

Access Policies

Recommendations for a jointly supported corpus of interoperable access policies

Technical Blueprint

Technical blueprint of a European compute and data continuum

SRIDA

A strategy and plan for the implementation of exascale research data federation and compute continuum for data-intensive science (SRIDA)

Annex 4: Network analysis (January 2025 Brainstorm)

